

Expected Number of k-level Crossings of a Random Algebraic Polynomial

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides asymptotic estimates for the expected number of real zeros and k-level crossings of a random algebraic polynomial of the form $a_0 \binom{n-1}{0}^{1/2} + a_1 \binom{n-1}{1}^{1/2} x + a_2 \binom{n-1}{2}^{1/2} x^2 + \dots + a_{n-1} \binom{n-1}{n-1}^{1/2} x^{n-1}$, where a_j ($j=0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1$) are independent standard normal random variables and k is constant independent of x . It is shown that these asymptotic estimates are much greater than those for algebraic polynomials of the form $a_0 + a_1 x + a_2 x^2 + \dots + a_{n-1} x^{n-1}$.

Key words: Independent, identically distributed random variables, random algebraic polynomial, random algebraic equation, real roots, domain of attraction of the normal law, slowly varying function

1991 Mathematics subject classification (amer. Math. Soc.): 60 B 99.

1. INTRODUCTION

Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \Pr)$ be a fixed probability space and let $\{a_j(\omega)\}$ for $j=0$ to $j=n-1$ be a sequence of independent random variables defined on Ω . The random algebraic polynomial was introduced in the pioneer work of Littlewood and Offord [5] and [6] as

$$Q(x) \equiv Q_n(x, \omega) = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} a_j(\omega) x^j$$

and since then has been greatly studied. Denote by $N_k(\alpha, \beta)$ the number of real roots of the equation $p(x) = K$ in the interval (α, β) and by $EN_k(\alpha, \beta)$ its expected value. In particular it is shown (for example see Kac [4] or Wilkins [8]) that if the coefficients are assumed to have a standard normal distribution and n is sufficiently large, $EN_0(-\infty, \infty) \sim (2/\pi) \log n$. Recently (see Farahmand [3]), it was shown that this asymptotic value remains valid for $EN_k(-\infty, \infty)$ as long as k is bounded. For k large such that $k^2/n \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, $EN_k(-\infty, \infty)$ asymptotically reduced to $(1/\pi) \log(n/k^2)$ in $(-1, 1)$ while it remains the same as for $k=0$ in $(-\infty, -1) \cup (1, \infty)$. In contrast, a random trigonometric polynomial

$$T(x) \equiv T_n(x, \omega) = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} a_j(\omega) \cos j\theta$$

has more roots in $(0, 2\pi)$. In fact, $EN_k(0, 2\pi) \sim 2n/\sqrt{3}$ for $k = o(\sqrt{n})$. Motivated by

the interesting results obtained in Littlewood and Offord [6] we considered the case when the coefficients $a_j(\omega)$ have variance $1/j!$. It is presumably the case, possibly under some mild conditions for K and for n sufficiently large, that $EN_k(-\infty, \infty)$ is $o(\sqrt{n})$. This author, however, was unable to make any substantial progress towards this conjecture. Instead in this paper we study the polynomials

$$P(x) \equiv P_n(x, \omega) = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} a_j(\omega) \binom{n-1}{j}^{1/2} x^j$$

This is indeed, the same as saying that the j th coefficient of $Q(x)$ has variance $\binom{n-1}{j}$. Besides the mathematical interest, as reported in Edelman and Kostlan [2] these polynomials have some relationship with physics [1]. We prove the following theorems. Theorem 1 was known to Edelman and Kostlan, however to be complete we give a proof here. Theorem 3, and its comparison with theorem 1, shows that for $p(x)$ there are as many extrema as the number of zero crossings. Therefore, unlike $Q(x)$, all the oscillations of $p(x)$ are between two zero crossings, asymptotically in expectation.

Theorem 1

If the coefficients a_j of $p(x)$ are independent standard normal random variables, then

$$EN_0(-\infty, \infty) = \sqrt{n-1}$$

Theorem 2

Denote $\mathcal{Y}(n) = (2n-1)!! / (2n)!!$ and assume $K^2 \mathcal{Y}(n) \rightarrow 0$.

With the same assumptions as in theorem 1 for the coefficients of $p(x)$, we have

$$EN_K(-\infty, \infty) \sim \sqrt{n-1}$$

2. A FORMULA FOR THE EXPECTED NUMBER OF REAL ROOTS

Let

$$A^2 = \text{var} \{P(X) - K\}, \tag{2.1}$$

$$B^2 = \text{var} \{P'(x)\}, \tag{2.2}$$

$$C = \text{cov} [\{P(x) - K\}, P'(x)] \tag{2.3}$$

$$\text{And } \eta = -CK / A \sqrt{A^2 B^2 - C^2}$$

Then by using the expected number of level crossings given by Cramer and Leadbetter [1] for our equation $P(x) - k = 0$, we can obtain

$$EN_K(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} \frac{B \sqrt{1 - C^2 / A^2 B^2}}{A} \phi\left(-\frac{K}{A}\right) [2\phi(\eta) + \eta \{2\phi(\eta) - 1\}] dx$$

Where as usual

$$\phi(t) = (2\Pi)^{-1/2} \int_{-\infty}^t \exp(-y^2 / 2) dy$$

and $\phi(t) = (2\Pi)^{-1/2} \exp(-t^2 / 2) dy$ Let $\Delta^2 = A^2 B^2 - C^2$ and $\text{erf}(x) = \int_0^x \exp(-t^2) dt$; then

we can write the extension of a formula obtained by Rice [7] for the case of $k=0$ as

$$EN_K(\alpha, \beta) = I_1(\alpha, \beta) + I_2(\alpha, \beta) \tag{2.4}$$

$$I_1(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\beta}^{\alpha} \frac{\Delta}{\Pi A^2} \exp\left(-\frac{B^2 K^2}{2 \Delta^2}\right) dx \tag{2.5}$$

$$I_2(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\beta}^{\alpha} \frac{\sqrt{2} KC}{\Pi A^3} \exp\left(-\frac{K^2}{2 A^2}\right) \text{erf}\left(\frac{KC}{\sqrt{2} A \Delta}\right) dx \tag{2.6}$$

3. PROOF OF THEOREM 1

We need the following, where (3.2) and (3.3) are obtained by differentiation of (3.1) and

$$A^2 = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{j} x^{2j} = (x^2 + 1)^{n-1} \tag{3.1}$$

$$B^2 = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{j} x^{2j-2} = (n-1)(x^2 + 1)^{n-3} (nx^2 - x^2 + 1) \tag{3.2}$$

$$C = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} j \binom{n-1}{j} x^{2j-1} = (n-1)x(x^2 + 1)^{n-2} \tag{3.3}$$

Therefore, since from (3.1) – (3.3)
 $\Delta^2 = A^2 B^2 - C^2 = (n-1)(x^2 + 1)^{2n-4}$
 from (2.4) - (2.6) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \text{EN}_0(0, \infty) &= \Pi^{-1} \int_0^\infty \frac{\Delta}{A^2} dx \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{n-1}}{\Pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{dx}{x^2 + 1} = \frac{\sqrt{n-1}}{2} \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

This gives the proof of theorem 1. It is, indeed, interesting to note that from (3.5)

$$\frac{\sqrt{n-1}}{\Pi(x^2 + 1)}$$

is the destiny function of the number of real zeros of P(X); see also [2, page 12]. Obtaining a closed form of the above density function is uncommon. An asymptotic result, for most cases, is the best that can be achieved.

4. PROOF OF THEOREM 2

Because $|\text{erf } u| < \sqrt{\Pi}/2$, it follows that from (2.6), (3.1), and (3.3) that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq I_2(-\infty, \infty) &\leq \frac{|K|}{\sqrt{2\Pi}} \int_{-\infty}^\infty \frac{C}{A^3} \exp\left(-\frac{K^2}{2A^2}\right) dx \\ &= \frac{2}{\sqrt{\Pi}} \int_0^{|K|/\sqrt{2}} e^{-v^2} dv \end{aligned}$$

if $v = |K|/(A\sqrt{2})$. Therefore, because $\text{erf } u \leq u$ when $u \geq 0$

$$0 \leq I_2(-\infty, \infty) \leq \frac{2}{\sqrt{\Pi}} \text{erf}\left(\frac{K}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \leq \min\left\{1, \frac{\sqrt{2}|K|}{\sqrt{\Pi}}\right\} \tag{4.1}$$

Moreover, it follows from (2.5), (3.1), (3.2) and (3.4) that

in which $s = (K^2/2) \{ (n-1) \sin^2\theta + \cos^2\theta \} \cos^{2n-4} \theta$.

$$\text{Therefore, } I_1(-\infty, \infty) = \frac{\sqrt{n-1}}{\Pi} \int_{-\infty}^\infty \frac{e^{-s}}{x^2 + 1} dx$$

In which $s = K^2 (nx^2 - x^2 + 1) / \{2 (x^2 + 1)^{n-1}\}$. If $x = \tan\theta$, we find that

$$I_1(-\infty, \infty) = \frac{2\sqrt{n-1}}{\Pi} \int_0^{\Pi/2} e^{-s} d\theta \tag{4.2}$$

$$I_1(-\infty, \infty) = \frac{2\sqrt{n-1}}{\Pi} \int_0^{\Pi/2} \{1 - (1 - e^{-s})\} d\theta = \sqrt{n-1} - R,$$

In which from [4],

$$0 \leq R = \frac{2\sqrt{n-1}}{\Pi} \int_0^{\Pi/2} (1 - e^{-s}) d\theta \leq \frac{2\sqrt{n-1}}{\Pi} \int_0^{\Pi/2} s d\theta = K^2 \beta_n$$

$$\beta_n = \frac{\sqrt{n-1}(3n-4)(2n-5)!!}{(2n-2)(2n-4)!!} = \sqrt{n-1} \gamma(n-2) \frac{3n-4}{2n-2}$$

A straight forward algebraic calculation shows that $\beta_{n+1} < \beta_n$ when $n \geq 2$. We conclude that that $0 \leq R \leq K^2 \beta_{j=K^2/2}$ and then that $R = o(\sqrt{n})$ because $K^2 = o\{\gamma^{-1}(n)\}$ and $\gamma(n) \sim \sqrt{n\Pi}$. When this last result is combined with (4.1), (4.2) and (2.4), it is clear that theorem 2 is true. In fact, we have actually proved the better result that

$$-\frac{K^2}{2} \leq EN_K(-\infty, \infty) - \sqrt{n-1} \leq \min\left\{1, \frac{\sqrt{2}|K|}{\sqrt{\Pi}}\right\},$$

from which we can also infer not only Theorem 2 but also that

$$EN_K(-\infty, \infty) = \sqrt{n-1} + O(1)$$

When K is bounded.

5. EXTREMA

The expected number of extrema of P(x), denoted by $EM(-\infty, \infty)$, is simply the expected number of real zeros of $P'(x) =$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n-1} a_j j \binom{n-1}{j}^{1/2} x^{j-1}$$

Therefore we apply $EN_0(-\infty, \infty)$ for $P'(x)$. To this end, by successive differentiation of (2.2) We obtain

$$A^2 = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} j^2 \binom{n-1}{j} x^{2j-2} = (n-1)(x^2+1)^{n-3} (nx^2 - x^2 + 1), \tag{5.1}$$

$$C = \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} j^2 (j-1) \binom{n-1}{j} x^{2j-3} = (n-1)(n-2)x(x^2+1)^{n-4} \{(n-1)x^2 + 2\} \tag{5.2}$$

And
$$B^2 = \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} j^2 (j-1)^2 \binom{n-1}{j} x^{2j-4} = (n-1)(n-2)(x^2+1)^{n-5} \{(n-1)(n-2)x^4 + 4(n-2)x^2 + 2\} \tag{5.3}$$

therefore, from (5.1) – (5.3) we obtain

$$\frac{\Delta}{A^2} = \frac{\sqrt{(n-2)\{(n-1)(n-2)x^4 + 2(n-1)x^2 + 2\}}}{(x^2 + 1)\{(n-1)x^2 + 1\}} \quad (5.4)$$

From (5.4) it then follows that, for all non-zero x

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Delta}{A^2 \sqrt{n-2}} = \frac{1}{x^2 + 1}$$

Then since $\Delta/A^2 \sqrt{n-2} \leq \sqrt{2}/(\sqrt{x^2 + 1})$ for all real x, the dominated convergent theorem for Lebesgue integrals shows that

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\Delta}{A^2 \sqrt{n-2}} dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{dx}{x^2 + 1} = \Pi$$

theorem 3 is then an intermediate consequence of this result.

6. CONCLUSION

By considering the polynomial of the form $Q(x) = Q_n(x, \omega) = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} a_j(\omega) x^j$

the expected number of real roots of the equation $p(x) = K$ is approximate to $\sim (2/\pi) \log n$. Hence the theorem.

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